

THE CURRENT STATE OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION LEADERS

O.H. Olimjonova

PhD, Teacher of the Department of Preschool Education, Namangan State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18995983>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the current state of ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education in the activities of preschool educational organization leaders. The study examines managerial, organizational-pedagogical, and monitoring mechanisms of leadership activity. Research methods such as analysis, comparison, questionnaires, and document analysis were used. The results indicate that professional competence of leaders, strategic planning, and internal quality control systems play a significant role in improving the quality of education in preschool institutions. Based on the findings, practical recommendations aimed at ensuring educational quality were developed.*

Keywords: *preschool educational organization, preschool education system, quality of education, educational effectiveness, educational process, pedagogical process, education quality management, quality management system, leadership activity, educational institution leader.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the attention and care provided by the state and the government to the preschool education system require the creation of necessary conditions for all heads of preschool educational organizations to engage in continuous self-development, conduct ongoing research, and organize the management process on a scientific basis in accordance with modern requirements. At the same time, this creates opportunities to ensure the quality and effectiveness of preschool education, which, in turn, places even greater responsibility on the leaders of preschool educational institutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

The article discusses the significance of structural management in ensuring the effectiveness of the preschool education process, the factors that determine the quality and efficiency of the preschool education system, and the current state of ensuring quality and effectiveness in the activities of heads of preschool educational organizations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

In the Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, special attention was paid to the issue of “introducing absolutely new approaches to the training, retraining, professional development, selection, and advancement of personnel with higher education for the preschool education system,” and a number of systemic problems and shortcomings hindering the successful implementation of state policy in the field of preschool education development were identified:

insufficient number of preschool educational institutions to ensure full coverage of children of preschool age;

underdevelopment of preschool education in rural areas;

unsatisfactory material and technical condition of preschool educational institutions;
lack of qualified pedagogical staff in preschool educational institutions;
shortage of managerial personnel in the preschool education system and their insufficient qualifications;

insufficient awareness among parents about the positive aspects and benefits of preschool education in the formation of a child's personality;

lack of modern educational and methodological materials and visual aids.

The effective and rational resolution of these problems and the creation of a developmental environment in preschool educational institutions constitute one of the essential tasks of their leaders.

The task of ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education in the activities of heads of preschool educational institutions is also reflected in the qualification requirements for the main positions of preschool education staff [1]. Accordingly, the head of a preschool educational institution is responsible for:

- further improving the preschool education system within the territory where the institution is located, strengthening its material and technical base, and effectively organizing its educational and methodological activities;

- providing the institution with highly competent, skilled, and qualified specialists;
- introducing modern educational programs and technologies aimed at the comprehensive intellectual, spiritual-aesthetic, and physical development of children into the educational process, and fundamentally improving their level of readiness for school;

- ensuring the full implementation of regulatory documents related to preschool education in practice;

- planning the activities of the institution and developing annual and перспективе work plans;

- approving work plans, curriculum-thematic plans, and annual calendar curricula of the institution;

- reviewing and approving the work plans of pedagogical staff and specialists and monitoring their full and high-quality implementation;

- taking measures to increase the coverage of preschool-age children in preschool education, especially ensuring the full enrollment of six-year-old children to provide quality preparation for primary education;

- introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process;

- creating appropriate conditions for the formation of general basic competencies and developmental domain competencies in children during the educational process;

- increasing the responsibility and accountability of pedagogical staff and employees in implementing the educational process and fulfilling the tasks defined in relevant documents;

- supervising the organization of open classes, seminars, competitions, and contests within the institution;

- analyzing all information related to the institution's activities, preparing reports, and continuously monitoring исполнитель discipline;

- providing organizational and methodological assistance to pedagogical staff and specialists in performing their official duties with quality, creating necessary working conditions, and ensuring labor discipline;

- encouraging the most active employees and, within the scope of authority, applying disciplinary measures to those who fail to fulfill their duties, as well as fostering a healthy moral environment within the team;

- establishing cooperation between the preschool educational institution and parents and studying parents' opinions regarding the development of the institution's activities;

- ensuring compliance with professional ethics rules, internal labor regulations, collective agreements, sanitary-hygienic requirements, occupational safety, technical and fire safety regulations, and creating a healthy competitive environment.

A modern competitive head of a preschool educational institution, managing the primary link of continuous education, is considered a responsible person for fulfilling the social order placed before the educational institution in his or her activities.

However, today in the management of preschool educational institutions, the following shortcomings can be observed:

- insufficient professional and scientific-methodological training of managerial personnel, lagging behind the content and methodological support of preschool education;

- failure to adhere to the principles of humanism and democracy in relations between managers and pedagogical staff;

- reliance on an authoritarian management style;

- lagging behind in acquiring the necessary methodological knowledge, skills, and competencies for the use of modern pedagogical and information technologies;

- inability to apply effective management methods in accordance with the requirements imposed on preschool educational institutions;

- lack of professional competencies among managerial personnel and insufficient ideological and political maturity;

- insufficient knowledge, skills, and competencies regarding advanced foreign experience in educational management;

- excessive involvement of most heads of preschool educational institutions in routine organizational work.

In the course of our research, surveys were conducted to identify the structural management competencies of heads of preschool educational institutions. Based on the survey results, a number of tasks were defined (presented in Appendix 1).

One of the main functions of structural management in preschool educational institutions is monitoring compliance with the requirements of the state standard. The purpose of monitoring compliance with state standard requirements is to determine the level of fulfillment of the requirements established by the state standard and, on this basis, to implement necessary measures to ensure the quality of education. In preschool educational institutions, ensuring educational effectiveness is achieved through monitoring the implementation of state requirements for the development of early and preschool-age children and the execution of the state curriculum for preschool education and upbringing [2].

The types of quality control in state preschool educational institutions include: internal control — carried out by the head of the state preschool educational institution, as well as by higher district (city) preschool education departments and the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional preschool education departments, and the Tashkent city preschool education department;

external control — carried out by state bodies and organizations authorized by law to inspect the activities of state preschool educational institutions;

public control — carried out in accordance with established procedures by public commissions organized within mahalla and rural citizens' assemblies;

national and international assessment — carried out on the basis of relevant government decisions and international agreements in cooperation with preschool education management bodies and other organizations, including international organizations.

The head of a preschool educational institution directly analyzes the activities of pedagogical staff during the internal control process and provides necessary instructions for organizing pedagogical processes.

Ensuring the effectiveness of preschool education processes on the basis of structural management requires organizing classes in accordance with the standard curriculum of preschool education institutions, distributing them by age groups, and monitoring their implementation.

In the preschool education system, the quality and effectiveness of education are determined by innovations being tested and implemented, as well as by the innovation processes organized, which are aimed at a specific goal — improving the educational process, developing children's knowledge, skills, and competencies, and совершенствование their activities.

The effectiveness of pedagogical processes organized in the preschool education system is determined by the development of children's knowledge, skills, and competencies and the growth of their learning achievement indicators.

Thus, in ensuring the quality and effectiveness of preschool education, the head of a preschool educational institution should focus on the following important factors, and the following results achieved in the process of interaction as a component of the pedagogical process organized in the institution are of particular significance for the development of children's personalities:

- development of children's activity and initiative;
- changes in children's psychological characteristics not strictly dependent on age;
- development of children's spiritual and cultural worldviews and concepts;
- formation and development of self-awareness and self-assessment skills in children;
- increase in the professional competence level of managerial staff and educators;
- emergence of collaborative activities between managerial and pedagogical staff;
- increase in the effectiveness of information exchange between educators and children;
- acceleration of the psychological adaptation of young teachers to professional activity and of newly enrolled children to the socio-educational environment.

Pedagogical practice shows that the formation of independent and free thinking skills and a rich spiritual worldview in preschool children occurs not only in specially organized pedagogical processes but also in the environment in which they live and study, in the interpersonal relations among members of the educational institution's staff, and in the educational environment emerging from these interactions. Moreover, the personal qualities, behavior, worldview, experience, knowledge, skills, and competencies of managerial staff and educators exert a specific influence on the development of children's personalities.

According to V.A. Slastenin and A.I. Mishenko, educators and learners, as subjects of the pedagogical process, are its main participants, and the pedagogical process is characterized as a specially organized process of interaction between educators and learners aimed at achieving educational objectives [7].

Based on these considerations, it can be stated that the classes organized in preschool educational institutions, more precisely the processes of education and upbringing and educational relations, constitute an integral pedagogical system. All forms of activities influencing children's personalities (walks, excursions, spiritual and educational events, sports competitions, fairs, etc.) and the processes of educational relations are interconnected and interdependent, possessing characteristics of mutual influence. The interrelation, interdependence, and unity of these constituent components express the integrity of the pedagogical process.

According to V.V. Sergeyev, to ensure effectiveness it is necessary to apply various methods and techniques, implement objective control and analyze its results, correct errors in a timely manner, and meet the requirements related to the competence of the inspector [6]. The form of internal control is directly reflected in the Three-Year перспективе Plan and the coordinated monthly plan (Work Journal) of the director of a state preschool educational institution [1]. In analyzing the current state of ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education in the activities of heads of preschool educational institutions, foreign experience can also be utilized. In Western literature, the term "improvement of structure" is generally not used. Instead, the following expressions are applied:

- making changes to the structure;
- replacing the structure;
- selecting the structure;
- integrating the structure.

Making changes to and replacing the structure is a continuous process in world practice and is considered one of the main indicators of managerial activity in any organization. The main factors of such changes are scientific and technological progress and strong competition. In U.S. companies, as well as in Western European and developed Eastern countries, management structures are on average replaced every 3–5 years.

Ways to improve the management structure:

1. Method of simplifying the existing structure. Reducing the number of management levels and granting more rights and authority to lower levels of management (decentralization). This method is considered among revolutionary approaches. Reducing the number of staff units or employees within them, transitioning from a matrix structure to a linear-functional structure, and ensuring that instead of one manager per 3–7 employees, there is one manager per 10–12 employees, that is, striving to achieve an optimal management norm.

2. Replacing a mechanically organized structure with an adaptive structure. A mechanically organized structure is characterized by the following negative aspects: rigidity in horizontal differentiation, strict hierarchical relations, standardized responsibility, a high degree of formalization, excessive centralization in decision-making, and the limited participation of most managers in this process, etc.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The reforms being implemented in the preschool education system of our country place the issue of ensuring the effectiveness of preschool education processes by managerial staff of preschool educational institutions on the agenda as an urgent task.

It is known that the effectiveness of preschool education processes is characterized by ensuring the formation of a healthy and well-developed personality of the child, awakening interest in learning, and preparing for systematic education. Therefore, on the basis of structural management of preschool education, it is of great importance to further strengthen the functioning

of this system, create a comprehensively favorable developmental educational environment and conditions in preschool educational institutions, and increase the coverage of preschool-age children.

Structural management expresses the interrelation between bodies and systems responsible for solving specific tasks within a preschool educational institution. The goals, functions, tasks, objects, and bodies of managing a preschool educational institution determine its organizational structure. The more perfect the management structure, the more effectively influence on the process of preschool education and upbringing is exercised.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” dated September 23, 2020, No. ORQ-637.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Preschool Education and Upbringing.” National Database of Legislation, December 17, 2019, No. 03/19/595/4160. <https://lex.uz/docs/4646908>
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2017 “On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Management of the Preschool Education System,” No. 5198.
4. Umarova M.Kh. *Theory and History of Pedagogy*. учебное пособие (Textbook). Publishing and Printing Creative House named after Chulpan. – Tashkent: 2018. p. 10.
5. Usmonov B.Sh., Rakhimov F.Kh., Dusmukhamedova M.Kh. *Integration of Education, Science and Production and Innovative Cooperation*. – Tashkent: “Cholpon” Publishing House, 2017.
6. Valijonov R., Qobulov O. *Fundamentals of Management*. – Tashkent: Tashkent State University, 1997.
7. Xaydarov A.I., Xalilova N.I. *General Psychology*. – Tashkent: Tashkent State Pedagogical University, 2010. p. 78.
8. Xo‘jayev A.A., Heikki Lentinen. *Ways to Improve Management Efficiency in the System of Secondary Specialized and Vocational Education of Uzbekistan*. – Tashkent, 2001. p. 126.